

#6 scientometric approach

#1 hirsch index

第3版

#8 interactive data exploration

Bornmann L

Van Egghe L

#3 bibliometric mapping

Boyack KW (2005)

#4

analytics

Thelwall M (2002)

Heimerike G (2003)

Bjorneborn L (2004)

#2 interpreting social science network analysis research

#5 structure-aware multi-scale navigation technique

科学计量学导论

#14 6th framework programme

Introduction to Scientometrics

李杰博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerryueb>

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说明

《科学计量学手册》（2024）和《科学计量学导论》（2025）

配套学习素材

本素材是在 2022 年《科学计量学导论》的基础上补充完善的新版本。随着《科学计量学手册》的出版，该素材将免费作为《科学计量学手册》的重要扩展资料（Supplementary Materials for Handbook of Scientometrics）。素材在整理过程中得到了蒋国华、武夷山、邱均平、陈超美、罗纳德·鲁索（Ronald Rousseau）、White HD、Ludo Waltman、Nees Jan van Eck、付慧真、侯剑华、唐莉、章成志、岳卫平、李洋等专家学者的支持和帮助。

期望本素材能为广大学生和青年学者的科学计量学学习提供一定的帮助。

Scientometricpedia: of the community, by the community, for the community.

开放获取权限

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科学计量学是量化的科学学，目标是创造一个可持续的科学发现与研究生态。

Scientometrics is the quantitative science of science, with the goal of creating a sustainable ecosystem for scientific discovery and research.

科学计量学的危机一直存在，我们只是视而不见。

The scientometrics crisis has always existed, but we have just been turning a blind eye to it.

1. 认识科学计量学

Peter Vinkler 的来信

Dear Dr. Jie Li!

The interpretation of “scientometrics is not the science of sciences but a science on science for science” (From Peter Vinkler, 05-07-2024).

“Science of science” – it is a term which may be understood as an exclusive body of knowledge or organization within all sciences. Earlier in the history of science in Europe there were theories considering the central role one of the disciplines. “Central role” may mean that methods, general views, laws, ethics, etc. of this “superior” science branch should be followed and applied by other disciplines. As central discipline e.g. theology later or parallel philosophy was accepted in the middle ages. Some theorists would think that there may exist some hierarchy among the disciplines also in natural sciences. In the ancient times astronomy later iatrochemistry, then alchemie was accepted as such a field. In the 19th century chemistry and from the end of the century physics, and from the middle of 20 century: biology. According to the view of several scientists – following Kant – a discipline may be the more exact the more mathematics it applies. I wanted to state that scientometrics should not be seen as a discipline superior to other disciplines. (Which may be concluded from the English phrase: “science of ”; other wise, it may be understood also as “a science from sciences”). It has no central role in the development of science. Its methods do not serve as models for another disciplines. In contrast, in my view: scientometrics is a discipline on each aspects of science, which do not belong to the scope of specific scientific branches. Its object is science as a whole and parts of it. I could not tell here in details that scientometrics deals primarily with the characteristics of information production, spread and impact, and it applies (mainly) quantitative methods.

And, last but not least: the activity of scientometrics should not be done as *l’art pour l’art*, i.e. for its own sake. Scientometrics should yield useful information for any discipline of science and also for the practical science policy on local and on country level or on discipline and field level, and on world scale. I think, the above are the most important reasons for writing the mentioned “bon mot”.

Best regards, Peter Vinkler

科学计量学 (Scientometrics)

科学计量学是科学的体温计！

(Scientometrics is the thermometer of science!)

科学计量学是“量化的科学学”，是对科学家活动和信息交流过程轨迹数据（包括论文发表记录、学术交流过程以及社会活动等）的数理建模分析（包含统计与概率论、微积分、图与矩阵分析等），其本质是为了揭示科学系统运行、科学发现以及科学演化等内在的科学特征与规律，为的是创造一个可持续的科学发现与研究生态。科学计量学可以使科学系统更透明、更开放（李杰，2023）。

Scientometrics is the *quantitative science of science*, focusing on the mathematical modeling analysis of trajectory data related to scientists' activities and information communication processes. Its essence is to reveal the inherent scientific characteristics and laws of the operation of scientific systems, scientific discoveries, and scientific evolution, with the goal of creating a sustainable ecosystem for scientific discovery and research. Scientometrics can make the scientific system more transparent and open (Jie Li, 2023).

图 1 Scientometrics 期刊（1978-2021）刊文主题聚类

图 2 截止到 2018 年来自 Journal of Informetrics、Scientometrics 以及 Journal of the Association for Information Science and Technology 三本刊物论文所形成的主题图

扫码在线查看图 1 网络版

扫码在线查看图 2 网络版

图 3 Scientometrics (1978-2022) 主要学者合著网络

图中，Scientometrics 的 TOP 10 高产学者都为普赖斯奖获得者，依次为 Glanzel Wolfgang (178 篇)、Schubert A (126 篇)、Bornmann Lutz (93 篇)、Leydesdorff Loet (93 篇)、Rousseau Ronald (90 篇)、Braun T (73 篇)、Egghe Leo (63 篇)、Thelwall Mike (62 篇)、Moed Henk F (54 篇) 以及 Vanraan AFJ (52 篇)。

文献计量学、科学计量学、信息计量学、网络计量学与替代计量学

Relationships among many subfields of library and information science fields Source:
Bjorneborn & Ingwersen (2004. p.1217)

术语	含义
Bibliometrics 文献计量学	Pritchard (1969) wrote: “Bibliometrics is the application of mathematics and statistical methods to books and other media of communication. It is the metrology of the information transfer process; its purpose is analysis and control of the process. In short: bibliometrics is the scientific study of recorded discourse”.
Scientometrics 科学计量学	Scientometrics (naukometria in Russian), a term proposed by Nalimov (Nalimov & Mul’chenko, 1969), is defined as the study of the quantitative aspects of science as a discipline or economic activity. It includes research evaluation and aspects of research policy. Yet, we note that nowadays the terms bibliometrics and scientometrics are used by many colleagues without any differentiation.
Informetrics 信息计量学	informetrics was proposed by Blackert and Siegel (1979) on the one hand, and by Nacke (1979) on the other. The study of the quantitative aspects of information in any form and in any social group.
Webmetrics 网络计量学	webmetrics is defined as the study of the quantitative aspects of the construction and use of information resources, structures and technologies on the Internet drawing on bibliometric and informetric approaches.
Altmetrics 替代计量学 (补充计量学)	Altmetrics(Alternative metrics) is a term referring to all metric techniques measuring new forms of performing, discussing or communicating science, especially through social media. Perhaps altmetrics should better be called social influmetrics (Rousseau & Ye, 2013) or social media metrics (Haustein, Costas, & Larivie´re, 2015).

参考文献: Rousseau, R., Egghe, L., & Guns, R. (2018). Chapter 1 - Introduction. In R. Rousseau, L. Egghe, & R. Guns (Eds.), *Becoming Metric-Wise* (pp. 1-10). Chandos Publishing.
<https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-102474-4.00001-7>

来源：《科学计量学导论》（2025年出版）

科学计量学发展简史 (1877-1989)

A Brief History of Scientometrics (Before 1990)

科学计量学发展简史 (1990-2019)

A Brief History of Scientometrics (After 1990)

试用库恩循环认识科学计量学的演化 (《科学革命的结构》(1962))
Try to use Kuhn's cycle to understand the scientometric evolution.

Reference: Rousseau, Ronald, Leo Egghe, and Raf Guns. Becoming metric-wise: A bibliometric guide for researchers. Chandos Publishing, 2018.
参考文献: 鲁索, 罗纳德, 利奥·埃格赫, 拉夫·冈斯。成为指标熟练者: 面向科研人员的文献计量学指南。Chandos出版社, 2018。

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元科学专业委员会
Metasciences Committee of BSTIS

Latest update: 2023-08-16

科学计量指标简史

A Brief History of Scientometric Indicators

查尔斯·古德哈特(Charles Albert Eric Goodhart, born 23 October 1936) is a British economist.

When a measure becomes a target, it ceases to be a good measure. (当一项测量手段本身成了目标, 那它就不再是一个好的测量手段) **Goodhart's Law (1975)**

立即指数 (Immediacy Index)

普赖斯指数 Price index

D. DE SOLLA PRICE, Citation measures of hard science, soft science, technology, and nonscience. In C. E. NELSON, D. K. POLLACK (Eds.), *Communication among Scientists and Engineers*. Heath, Lexington, MA, 1970, pp. 3-22.

h-指数 h-index

Hirsch J. E. An index to quantify an individual's scientific research output [J]. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences*, 2005, 102(14): 10249-10252.

期刊特征分数 Eigenfactor Score

C. T. Bergstrom (2007). Eigenfactor: Measuring the value and prestige of scholarly journals. *PLoS News* 6: 642.

HC指数 HC-index

Sidiropoulos A., Katsaros D., Manolopoulos Y (2007) Generalized h-index for disclosing latent facts in citation networks. *Scientometrics* 72(2):283-300

e指数 e-index

Zhang, C.-T. The e-index: Complementing the h-index for Excess Citations. *PLoS ONE*, 2009, 4(3): 45429.

SJR

González-Pereira B, Giménez-Bote V.P., Moyá-Aguado F (2010) A new approach to the metric of journals' scientific prestige: the SJR indicator. *Journal of Informetrics* 4(3):379-391.

Selmao SJR指数 Scimago SJR indicator

Start

1963

期刊影响力因子 Journal Impact Factor

Garfield, E. and Sher, I.H. (1963). New factors in the evaluation of scientific literature through citation indexing. *Amer. Doc.* 14: 195-201.

1975

半衰期 Half life

Linc, M. B. (1970). The "half-life" of periodical literature: Apparent and real obsolescence. *Journal of Documentation*, Vol. 26 No. 1, pp. 46-54.

1970

网络影响力因子 Web Impact Factor

Ingwersen, P. The calculation of Web impact factors. *Journal of Documentation*, 1998, 54(2): 236-243.

1998

引用迟滞/睡美人 sleeping beauty

van Raan, A.J.J. Sleeping Beauties in science. *Scientometrics*, 2004, 59, 467-472.

2004

皇冠指数 crown indicator

Van Raan, A. J. J. (2005). Measuring science: capita selecta of current main issues. In H. F. Moed, W. Glänzel, & U. Schmoch (Eds.), *Handbook of quantitative science and technology research* (pp. 19-59). New York: Springer.

2005

g指数 g-index

Eggle L. Theory and practise of the g-index [J]. *Scientometrics*, 2006, 69(1): 151-52.

2006

R指数和AR指数 R-index & AR-index

Jie, D.H.; Liang, L.M.; Rousseau, R. & Eggle, L. The R- and AR-indices: Complementing the h-index. *Chinese Science Bulletin*, 2007, 52(6):858-863

2007

hm指数 hm indices

Scherer M (2008) To share the fame in a fair way: HM indices H for multi-authored manuscripts. *New Phys*, 10(6):2019.

2008

W指数 W-index

Wu, Qiang (2009). "The w-index: A measure to assess scientific impact by focusing on widely cited papers". *Journal of the American Society for Information Science and Technology*

2009

r指数 r-index

Vinkler, P. (2009). The r-index: A new indicator for assessing scientific impact. *Journal of Information Science*, 35(3), 602-612.

2010

标准化影响系数 Standardized impact per paper- SNIP

Moed H.F. Measuring contextual citation impact of scientific journals[J]. *Journal of Informetrics*, 2010, 4(3): 265-277.

获奖指数 Prize Winner Index (PWI)

Bonnamm, L. & Hunschuld, R. (2023). How to measure research performance of single scientists? A proposal for an index based on scientific prizes: The Prize Winner Index (PWI). *arXiv preprint arXiv:2303.18007*.

M指数 M-index

Misrao, V.V. (2020) New Indices of Publication Activity. *Inter. Russ. Acad. Sci.* 9(1): 618-624.

Ψ指数 Ψ-index

Lafabou, H. (2020). Ψ-index: A new overall productivity index for actors of science and technology. *Journal of Informetrics*, 14(4), 1010-6.

颠覆性指数 Disruptive Index

Funk R.J., Owen-Smith J. A dynamic network measure of technological change [J]. *Management science*, 2017, 63(3): 794-817.

相对引用率 RCR

Hutchins, B. L., Yuan, X., Anderson, J. M., & Santangelo, G. M. (2016). Relative citation ratio (RCR): a new metric that uses citation rates to measure influence at the article level. *PLoS biology*, 14(9), e1002541.

p指数 p-index

Senanayake, U., Piraveenan, M., & Zomaya, A. Y. (2014). The p-index: Ranking scientists using network dynamics. *Procedia Computer Science*, 20, 466-477.

Z指数 Z-index

Petersen, A. M., & Succi, S. (2013). The Z-index: A geometric representation of productivity and impact which accounts for information in the entire rank-citation profile. *Journal of Informetrics*, 7(3), 421-432.

Uzzi新颖性测度 Uzzi Novelty测度

Brian Uzzi et al (2013). Atypical Combinations and Scientific Impact. *Science*, 342, 468-472. DOI:10.1126/science.1240474

i10指数 i10-index

Waltman, L., & Eck, N. J. (2015). Field-normalized citation impact indicators and the choice of an appropriate counting method. *Journal of Informetrics*, 9(4), 472-484.

Q指数 Q-index

Bartneck C, Kokkelmans S (2011) Detecting h-index manipulation through self-citation analysis. *Scientometrics* 87(1):85-98.

I3指数 I3 index

LEYLANDSLOTT, L. AND HANSEN, L. (2011). Integrated impact indicators compared with impact factors: An alternative research design with policy implications. *J. Am. Soc. Inf. Sci.*, 62: 2153-2166.

古德哈特定律 (Goodhart's Law)

2023

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如果深谱科学计量学指标的学者利用指标以谋私利, 这将是科学计量研究的悲哀和学术界的最大丑闻 (李杰, 2023-6-6)。

If scholars who have a deep understanding of scientometric indicators use these indicators for personal gain, it would be a tragedy for scientometric research and the greatest scandal in the academic community (Jie Li, 2023-6-6) .

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元科学专业委员会
Metasciences Committee of BSTIS

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科学计量学工具简史

A Brief History of Scientometric Tools

卡尔·马克思
(Karl Heinrich Marx, 1818-1883)

马克思主义关于人类起源的理论,是与马克思和恩格斯运用辩证唯物主义历史唯物主义的原理,对科学发展成果的总结。马克思和恩格斯在他们的著作中,既全面论述了猿如何在劳动的推动下转变为在猿的方面和它不同的生物——人,指出劳动是从猿到人转变过程的主要推动力,又反复强调了使用和制造工具在人类形成中的地位和作用。说明制造工具是人类劳动产生,人类形成和人类社会出现的标志。(来源文献:罗先德《马克思主义论制造工具在人类形成中的地位和作用——纪念马克思逝世一百周年》,《西北民族大学学报(哲学社会科学版)》,1983(01):3-12)

人类和动物除了智慧上的差别以外,最大的区别并不是我们会使用工具,而是我们会制造工具。

工具是认识科学演化的重要方面

Alexander Schneider (亚历山大·施奈德): 科学领域的4个发展阶段

Schneider, A. M. (2009). Four stages of a scientific discipline; four types of scientist. Trends in Biochemical Sciences, 34(5), 217-223.

Alexander Schneider, Ph.D.

Dr. Schneider is the CEO of CureLab Oncology, bringing more than 25 years of biotech and entrepreneurial experience. He is currently a senior research fellow of molecular biology at the University of Ariel, Israel, and an editorial board member for the journals Aging and International Reviews of Immunology.

图例Legend

约翰·德斯蒙德·贝尔纳奖简史

A Brief History of John Desmond Bernal Prize

贝尔纳 (John Desmond Bernal, 1901-1971)

约翰·德斯蒙德·贝尔纳 (英语: John Desmond Bernal, 1901年5月10日—1971年9月15日), 英国科学家, 出生于爱尔兰, 毕业于剑桥大学, 主要研究方向为X射线晶体学, 但是在科学史方面也有很多著作。贝尔纳在第二次世界大战时曾加入英国皇家海军。

约翰·德斯蒙德·贝尔纳奖 (John Desmond Bernal Prize) 是由社会科学研究学会 (Society for Social Studies of Science, 4S) 每年颁发的奖项, 授予在科学与技术研究 (Science and Technology Studies, STS) 跨学科领域中作出杰出贡献的学者。该奖项于1981年由尤金·加菲尔德 (Eugene Garfield) 的支持下设立。该奖项以科学家约翰·德斯蒙德·贝尔纳 (John Desmond Bernal) 的名字命名。

加菲尔德博士于1981年设立贝尔纳奖

The Society for Social Studies of Science (4S)

<p>Little Science, Big Science</p> <p>1981 Derek de Solla Price (1922 - 1983)</p>	<p>The Sociology of Science</p> <p>1982 Robert King Merton (1910 - 1983)</p>	<p>The Structure of Scientific Revolutions</p> <p>1983 Thomas Samuel Kuhn (1922-1996)</p>	<p>Science and Civilization in China</p> <p>1984 Noel Joseph Terence Montgomery Needham (1900-1995)</p>	<p>The Scientist's Role in Society: A Comparative Study</p> <p>1985 Joseph Ben-David</p>	<p>The Word and the World: Explorations in the Form of Sociological Analysis</p> <p>1986 Michael Mulcahy</p>	<p>The Economics of Industrial Innovation</p> <p>1987 Christopher Freeman</p>	<p>Selling Science: How the Press Covers Science and Technology</p> <p>1988 Dorothy Nollan</p>
<p>Science and the Social Order</p> <p>1995 Bernard Barber</p>	<p>Natural Symbols</p> <p>1994 Mary Douglas</p>	<p>Astronomy Transformed</p> <p>1993 David Edge</p>	<p>Laboratory Life (with Steve Woolgar)</p> <p>1992 Bruno Latour</p>	<p>By the Sweat of Thy Brow: Work in the Western World (with Joseph Gies)</p> <p>1991 Mehin Kranzberg</p>	<p>Networks of Power: Electrification in Western Society, 1880-1930</p> <p>1990 Thomas Hughes</p>	<p>The Scientific Imagination</p> <p>1989 Gerald Holton</p>	
<p>Knowledge and Social Imagery</p> <p>1996 David Bloor</p>	<p>The Golem: What Everyone Should Know about Science (with Trevor Pinch)</p> <p>1997 Harry Collins</p>	<p>Scientific Knowledge and Sociological Theory</p> <p>1998 Barry Barnes</p>	<p>The Great Devonian Controversy: The Shaping of Scientific Knowledge among Germanly Specialists</p> <p>1999 Martin J.S. Rudwick</p>	<p>A Cyborg Manifesto: Science, Technology, and Socialist-Feminism in the Late Twentieth Century</p> <p>2000 Donna Haraway</p>	<p>Leviathan and the Air-Pump: Hobbes, Boyle, and the Experimental Life (with Simon Schaffer)</p> <p>2001 Steven Shapin</p>		
<p>A Social History of American Technology</p> <p>2007 Ruth Schwartz Cowan</p>	<p>Of bicycles, bakelites and bulbs: Toward a Theory of Sociotechnical Change</p> <p>2006 Wabe Bijker</p>	<p>Mechanizing proof: computing, risk, and trust</p> <p>2005 Donald MacKenzie</p>	<p>Controlling Chemicals</p> <p>2004 Sheila Jasanoff</p>	<p>Re-Thinking Science (with Michael Gibbon and Peter Scott)</p> <p>2003 Hoga Nowotny</p>	<p>The Laws of the Markets</p> <p>2002 Michel Callon</p>		
<p>Laboratory Life (with Bruno Latour)</p> <p>2008 Steve Woolgar</p>	<p>Epistemic Cultures: How the Sciences Make Knowledge</p> <p>2006 Karin Knorr Cetina</p>	<p>Rationality and Ritual: The Windscale Inquiry and Nuclear Decision in Britain</p> <p>2005 Brian Wynne</p>	<p>Reflections on Gender and Science</p> <p>2004 Evelyn Fox Keller</p>	<p>Disciplining Reproduction: American Life Scientists and the 'Problem of Sex'</p> <p>2003 Adele Clarke</p>	<p>The Science Question in Feminism</p> <p>2002 Sandra Harding</p>		
<p>The Woman in the Body: A Cultural Analysis of Reproduction (1987), The Egg and the Sperm: How Science Has Constructed a Romance Based on Stereotypical Male-Female Roles (1991)</p> <p>2008 Emily Martin</p>	<p>The Social Construction of Technological Systems: New Directions in the Sociology and History of Technology (with Wabe Bijker and Thomas F. Hughes)</p> <p>2009 Karin Knorr Cetina</p>	<p>Ciencia, Tecnología y Sociedad en América Latina (Science, Technology and Society in Latin America)</p> <p>2010 Evelyn Fox Keller</p>	<p>Representation in Scientific Practice</p> <p>2012 Adele Clarke</p>	<p>Plans and Situated Actions: The Problem of Human-machine Communication</p> <p>2002 Lucy Suchman</p>	<p>Power, action, and belief: a new sociology of knowledge</p> <p>2014 Lucy Suchman</p>		
<p>Beamtimes and Lifetimes: The World of High Energy Physicists (1988)</p> <p>2019 Sharon Trawick</p>	<p>Autonomous Technology (1977), 'Do Artifacts Have Politics?' (1980), The Whale and the Reactor (1986)</p> <p>2019 Langdon Winner</p>	<p>The Social Shaping of Technology (with Donald MacKenzie, 1982), Pressed for Time: The Acceleration of Life in Digital Capitalism (2015)</p> <p>2018 Trevor Pinch</p>	<p>Beyond the Natural Body (1994), The Male Pill (2003), Telecare and the Transformations of Healthcare (2011)</p> <p>2017 Hebe Vessuri</p>	<p>Backdoor to Eugenics (2004)</p> <p>2016 Michael Lynch</p>	<p>Futures of Science and Technology in Society, Nanotechnology and its governance</p> <p>2016 Michael Lynch</p>		
<p>1 Sharon Trawick</p>	<p>2 Langdon Winner</p>	<p>1 Judy Wajcman</p>	<p>2 Nelly Oudshoorn</p>	<p>1 Arie Epp</p>	<p>2 Trey Duster</p>	<p>1 Joan Fujimura</p>	<p>2 Warwick Anderson</p>

2. 给科学计量学入门者推荐的读物*

Recommended Readings for Beginners in Scientometrics

经典著作

* 列表将动态持续更新。

入选规则：具有创新性研究的专著或系统性工具书。

1. 埃利泽·盖斯勒著. 周萍等译, 武夷山校译. 科学技术测度体系[M]. 北京: 科学技术文献出版社, 2004. (普赖斯奖获得者作品)
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入选规则：领域内作出开创性贡献的论文。

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综合期刊代表成果

入选规则：来自国际顶级综合期刊 *Nature*、*Science*、*PNAS* 及其子刊的科学计量研究前沿或热点成果。

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影响力的三个维度。

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3. 给科学计量学初学者推荐的入门视频

Introductory Videos for Beginners in Scientometrics

(以下信息是通过网络整理，仅用于教学使用)

拉斐尔 《雅典学派》（1509—1511 年）

以“集智”思想集成科学共同体智慧，开创科学计量学发展新篇章。

Scientometric: Making The Scientific System More Open and Transparent!

科学计量学：让科学系统更开放、更透明！

What is Bibliometrics?
什么是文献计量学?

Dr. Howard White:
Visualization and
Bibliometrics

什么是共被引分析?

科学计量学导论
Introduction to
Scientometrics

什么是影响因子? What is
impact factor

什么是 h 指数? What is H
index?

科学、科学家与科学计
量学 Science, Scientists
and Scientometrics

引文索引 50 年, 采访加菲
尔德 50 Years of Citation
Indexing_ A visit with Dr.
Eugene Garfield

文献计量学与补充计量学导
论 Bibliometrics and
Altmetrics_ An Introduction

引文分析的历史
Citation Analysis History

作者引文分析
Author Citation Analysis

理解影响因子 Understanding
the impact factor

理解引文与文献计量学
研究 Understanding
Citations and Research
Bibliometrics

负责任的科学计量学
Responsible scientometrics_
All of the questions; none of
the answers

引文影响是什么以及如何测
量? Citation Impact What is

我们如何减少学术界对指标的滥用 Stefanie Haustein-How can we reduce the misuse of metrics in academia

自引是知识积累的正常特征还是... Vincent Larivière-“Are self-citations a normal feature of knowledge accumulation or ...”

什么是元科学？ What is Metascience

研究领域的形成、发展和消亡

描绘研究领域的学术格局 Delineating the Scholarly Landscape of a Research Field

第 14 届国际科学计量学与信息计量学学会会议开幕式 14th International Society of Scientometrics and Informetrics Conference Opening Ceremony

24 小时科学知识图谱活动 24-Hour Science Mapping Event

Katy Börner 博士的科学地图讲座 Mapping Science Lecture with Dr. Katy Börner

科学地图和出版分析-Kevin Boyack.mp4 Mapping of Science and the Analytics of Publishing - Kevin Boyack

对于计量学指标的想法与事实 Wolfgang Glänzel Thoughts and facts on bibliometric indicators in the light

发现谢伯德引文 Eugene Garfield Discovering Shepards Citations

预印本与开放同行评议 Preprinting and Open Peer Review

莱顿宣言 The Leiden
Manifesto for Research
Metrics-HD

开放科学的五个学派 Five
Schools of Open
Science.mp4

什么是研究评价的旧金山宣
言? Introduction to the San
Francisco Declaration on
Research Assessment (DORA)

Top 100 篇论文, 自然探
索史上引用最多的研究
The top 100 papers,
Nature explores the most-
cited research of all time

《自然》150年 引文空间
网络

制作《自然》150年引文网
络 On the making of Nature
150

库恩-科学革命的结构
Thomas Kuhn_ The
Structure of Scientific
Revolutions

库恩-常规科学
Thomas Kuhn, normal
science

库恩-科学革命
Thomas Kuhn, scientific
revolutions

库恩-不可通约性及进展
Thomas Kuhn,
incommensurability and
progress.mp4

卡尔波普尔-三个世界
Sir Karl Raimund Popper on
the Three World (1989)

科学学导论
Intro to Science of Science

《巴拉巴西成功定律》导
读

《给科学家的科学思维》导
读

《科学革命的结构》导
读

VOSviewer 导论
Visual exploration of
scientific literature using
VOSviewer and
CitNetExplorer

王大顺学术报告：科学的
科学 Dashun Wang-
Distilling Lessons from the
Science of Science

王大顺讲座：解读科学的科
学。Decoding the Science of
Science - Dashun Wang

王大顺讲座：量化失败
Quantifying Failure -
Dashun Wang

评估学术生涯 E04 Björn
Hammarfelt-Assessing
academic careers

男女合作与学术职业 E07
Marek Kwiek-Man-Woman
Collaboration and Academic
Careers

网络的模块化值
Modularity

什么是 DIKW? What is
the DIKW Pyramid

什么是中介中心性? What is
Degree Centrality_.mp4

诺贝尔奖获得者马
丁·查尔菲提出的关于
科学家的五个神话
The five myths about
scientists according to
Nobel Laureate Martin
Chalvie

好奇驱动研究的重要性，
诺贝尔奖获得者巴里·马
歇尔
The importance of curiosity
driven research, Nobel
Laureate, Barry Marshall

创意从何而来? 诺贝尔奖获
得者蒂姆·亨特
Where do Ideas come from_
Nobel Laureate Tim Hunt

科学家是否应该对他们的工作保守秘密？诺贝尔奖获得者蒂姆·亨特
Should scientists be secretive about their work_ Nobel Laureate Tim Hunt

永远不要写下你不理解的东西。"- 诺贝尔奖获得者奥利弗·史密斯斯
Never write down something you don't understand_ - Nobel Laureate Oliver Smithies

幸运是否在科学发现中扮演了一部分角色？"- 诺贝尔奖获得者巴里·马歇尔
Does luck play a part in scientific discovery_ Barry Marshall, Nobel Laureate

给年轻科学家的忠告
E.O. Wilson_ Advice to young scientists

良好的团队合作和糟糕的团队合作
good teamwork and bad teamwork

什么是元科学？
What is Metascience

科学学的集成 A
Synthesis for The Science of Science - Cassidy Sugimoto

元科学 - 定位过去，构想未来
Metascience -Situating the past, imagining the future

2003 年美国科学院 Mapping knowledge domains 会议
Poster Presentations 珍贵视频 -开启了科学知识图谱研究的热潮

CiteSpace 原理及应用（慕课）

Principles and Applications of CiteSpace (Online Course)

通道一：CiteSpace 原理及应用 慕课

<https://mooc1-1.chaoxing.com/course/212680405.html>

通道二：CiteSpace 原理及应用 慕课

<https://space.bilibili.com/508721901/channel/collectiondetail?sid=496360>

通道三：CiteSpace 慕课视频（知乎）

<https://www.zhihu.com/people/safetyscience/zvideos>

课程主讲：陈超美（Chen Chaomei）

陈超美，男，1960 年生于北京。先后就读于南开大学数学专业（1979-1983），牛津大学计算专业（1990-1991）和英国利物浦大学计算机专业（1991-1995）。先后就职于英国格拉斯哥卡利多尼安大学（1995-1997），英国布鲁内尔大学（1998-2001）和美国德雷塞尔大学（2001 至今）。目前担任美国德雷塞尔大学计算与信息学院教授。2003 年以来，创建开发了广泛应用于识别和了解科学文献中结构及动态的可视化分析软件 CiteSpace。主要研究领域包括视觉分析推理，复杂自适应系统结构和动态关键信息的评估以及科学和技术发展中新兴趋势和潜在变革性变化的识别，特别是运用计算和视觉分析方法。著有《Representing Scientific Knowledge: The Role of Uncertainty》(Springer 2017)，《The Fitness of Information: Quantitative Assessments of Critical Information》(Wiley, 2014)，《Turning Points: The Nature of Creativity》(Springer, 2011)（中译本：《转折点：创造性的本质》）和《Mapping Scientific Frontiers: The Quest for Knowledge Visualization》(Springer 2003, 2013)（中译本：《科学前沿图谱：知识可视化的探索》）。分别于 2002 年和 2016 年创办国际期刊 Information Visualization 和 Frontiers in Research Metrics and Analytics，并任主编。发表学术论文 300 余篇，出版著作 10 余部，Google Scholar 被引 28000 余次。研究项目获得来自美国国家科学基金会 (NSF)、欧盟、英国工程和物理科学研究委员会、英国图书馆和信息委员会，以及 Elsevier、IMS Health、Lockheed Martin 和 Pfizer 等资助。

CiteSpace 官网：<https://citespace.podia.com/>

4. 给科学计量学初学者推荐的微信矩阵

Recommended WeChat Groups for Scientometrics Beginners

(按照提供信息的先后顺序)

科学知识前沿图谱

开放科学计量学实验室

林墨

熊彼特的厨房

《科学计量学》

武汉大学科教管理与评价
中心

集智俱乐部

OpenScience

科学学

看见 Science

中国科学学与科技政策研
究会

图智决策

5. 科学计量与知识图谱系列丛书

Book Series of Scientometrics and Knowledge Mapping

丛书主编：李杰

丛书目录（共 13 本图书，◎正在出版过程中；●已出版）：

● BibExcel 科学计量与知识网络分析（第三版）

● CiteSpace 科技文本挖掘及可视化（第三版）

● MuxViz 多层网络分析与可视化（译）

● R 科学计量数据可视化（第二版）

● 引文网络分析与可视化（译）

● Python 科学计量数据可视化

● 科学学的历程

● 科学计量学手册

◎ VOSviewer 科学知识图谱原理及应用

◎ Gephi 网络可视化导论

◎ 专利计量与数据可视化（译）

◎ 现代文献综述指南（译）

◎ 科学知识图谱导论

* 系列丛书配套免费资料下载地址：<https://citespace.lanzouj.com/b016zh5je>

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6. 科学计量指标 “周期表”

Periodic Table of Scientometric Indicators

Periodic Table of Scientometric Indicators

EC3 metrics		Legend																		Lnk				
h	P	Basic Indicators									Webmetric Indicators (1.0)									Lnk				
		Bibliometric Indicators						h-index based Indicators			Altmetric Indicators									Lnk				
IF	AF	CS	JCS	FCS	FNCI	NJI	JCS	RgC	MASC	GSC	GSh	Lk	PM	FacL	APV	RGV	Vw			Fav	MR	AP	RGV	WS
SJR	EF	SNIP	I3	CI	MCS	MNCS	MCRS	MSNCS	MASP	GSP	Sub	BM	TwM	FacS	ADV	RGD	Dwd							
IPP	CPP	CPPex	ANCP	TNCS	RAI	RSI	RCR	RDCP	JAR	Com	PuPC	NM	WC	FacC	Afr	RGI	Ck							
%SC	%Pnc	PR	LogZ	IK	TI	STP	NPJ	WCH	Rev	F1Re	GoRev	MoH	ARev	Play	Afg	RGfr	FTV							
PT1	PT10	PT50	HCP	Q1	PWoS	NHCP	PTRJ	Exp	Q&A	F1R	GoRat	MoR	ARat	PS	OS	RGfg	AV							
PCol	%CoA	NCoI	ICol	SL	EN	Exc	Sav	ReR	F1FFa	GoRea	MoS	RcCU	RCU	BoD	AA	AAS	DIL							
i10	g	a	h(2)	hg	q2	r	ar	k	f	m	m-q	Ch	Th	Dh-T	n	Mh								
h5	Nh	Sls	Sih-T	Hw	Hm	Th	I10	v	e	hla	Mh	RC	CC	Ch	CSS	π								
h5-m	2gh	Rbhm	h2-l	h2-c	h2-u	h3	p	Hbar	Mhm	w	b	Gh	SPh	hint	Hrat	πv								

EC3 metrics
evaluación científica

El profesional de la
información

图 4 科学计量指标 “周期表”

来源: <https://ec3metrics.com/wp-content/uploads/2018/06/tablaper3.pdf>

7. 情报发现的新范式-知识可视化展览⁺

A New Paradigm of Information Discovery: Knowledge Visualization Exhibition

⁺ 情报发现的新范式-知识可视化系列海报曾先后在上海图书馆、清华大学图书馆、江苏大学图书馆和首都师范大学进行线上或线下的展览。2022年，将该场景系统布置在了中国科学院文献情报中心展厅，欢迎参观。

图 5 情报发现的新范式-知识可视化展览

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8. 杰出科学家谱系

普赖斯奖简史 A Brief History of Price Memorial Medal

Derek de Solla Price
(1922 - 1983)

德瑞克·约翰·德索拉·普赖斯 (Derek John de Solla Price, 1922年1月22日—1983年9月3日), 英国物理学家、科学史家, 被认为是科学计量学之父。其发表的经典著作《大科学, 小科学》和《巴比伦以来的科学》成为研究科学史和科学计量学的重要文献。

- Price D J. The exponential curve of science[J]. Discovery, 1956, 17:240-43.
- Price D J. The science of science[J]. Discovery, 1956, 17:159-80.
- Price D J. Science Since Babylon[M]. Yale University Press, 1961.
- Price D J. Little Science, Big Science[M]. New York: Columbia University Press, 1963.
- Price, D. J. D. S. Networks of scientific papers. Science, 1965, 149(3683), 510-515.
- Price D J. Scientific foundations of science policy[J]. Nature, 1965, 206:233-38.

《巴比伦以来的科学》

《小科学, 大科学》

1984 — 1985 — 1986 — 1987 — 1988

Eugene Garfield
(1928-2017)
(USA)

Michael J. Moravcsik
(1928-1989)
(USA)

Tibor Braun
(1932-2022)
(Hungary)

Vasily V. Nalimov
(1910-1997)
(Soviet Union)

Henry Small
(1941-)
(USA)

Francis Narin
(1934-)
(USA)

1997 — 1995 — 1993 — 1989

Belver C. Griffith
(1931-1999)
(USA)

Ben Martin
(1952-)
(UK)

John Irvine
(1951-)
(UK)

Robert K. Merton
(1910-2003)
(USA)

Anthony F. J. Van Raan
(1945-)
(The Netherlands)

András Schubert
(1946-)
(Hungary)

András Schubert
(1946-)
(Hungary)

Bertram C. Browkes
(1910-1991)
(UK)

Jan Vlasby
(1937-2010)
(Czechoslovakia)

1999 — 2001 — 2003 — 2005

Henk F. Meuld
(1951-2021)
(The Netherlands)

Wolfgang Glänzel
(1955-)
(Germany/Hungary)

Ronald Rousseau
(1949-)
(Belgium)

Leo Eghe (1952-)
(Belgium)

Leo Eghe (1952-)
(Belgium)

Loet Leydesdorff
(1948-2023)
(The Netherlands)

Peter Ingwersen
(1947-)
(Denmark)

Peter Ingwersen
(1947-)
(Denmark)

Howard D. White
(1936-)
(USA)

2015 — 2013 — 2011 — 2009 — 2007

Mike Thelwall
(1965-)
(UK)

Blaise Cronin
(1949-)
(USA)

Blaise Cronin
(1949-)
(USA)

Olle Persson
(1949-)
(Sweden)

Olle Persson
(1949-)
(Sweden)

Peter Vinkler
(1941-)
(Hungary)

Michel Zitt
(1947-)
(France)

Michel Zitt
(1947-)
(France)

Katherine W. McCain
(1944-)
(USA)

2017 — 2019 — 2021 — 2023

Judi Bar-Ilan
(1958-2019)
(Israel)

Lutz Bornmann
(1967)
(Germany)

Lutz Bornmann
(1967)
(Germany)

Ludo Waltman
(1982-)
(The Netherlands)

Ludo Waltman
(1982-)
(The Netherlands)

Kevin W. Boyack
(1962-)
(USA)

Kevin W. Boyack
(1962-)
(USA)

Richard Klavans
(1948-)
(USA)

Richard Klavans
(1948-)
(USA)

9. OA 科学知识图谱指南下载

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BibExcel 中文指南
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2020年8月25日-北京

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李杰¹ 副研究员 陈超美² 教授
1. 中国科学院文献情报中心
2. 美国德雷塞尔大学计算机与信息科学系

李杰博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/jerrycueb>
陈超美博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/u/ChaomeiChen>

谨以此手册献给科学知识图谱的爱好者!

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感谢陈超美教授的无私奉献! 谨以此手册
献给在 CiteSpace 学习中的所有人!

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2015年5月3日-北京

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杭州盛觉网络科技有限公司(ap)
元宇宙高地 (metaverse)

元宇宙 (t)
metaverse

VOSviewer Gallery

李杰 博士
lijie_jerry@126.com

谨以此手册献给科学知识图谱的爱好者!

SCI² 中文指南

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2021年12月31日 北京

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VOSviewer 中文指南

第 1 版

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科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/lijerryclub/>

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最近更新: 2018年7月21日 北京

科学知识前沿图谱方法与工具

Mapping Knowledge Domains

李杰
电子邮件: lijie_jerry@126.com
科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/lijerryclub/>

2018年5月20日

科学领域叠加图分析指南(第 1 版)

How to Create an Overlay Map of Science Using the Web of Science

Ken Riopelle, Loet Leydesdorff, 李杰
电子邮件: lijie_jerry@126.com
科学网博客: <http://blog.sciencenet.cn/lijerryclub/>

参考格式: Ken Riopelle, Loet Leydesdorff, 李杰 (2014). 科学领域叠加图分析指南(第 1 版). <https://www.leydesdorff.net/overlaytoolkit/>

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2014年3月30日 北京

1

提取码: jsis

10. 推荐刊物

11. 学者寄语

2023 年在组织撰写《科学计量学手册》期间，专门邀请了若干普赖斯奖为青年学者撰写了寄语。期待科学计量学健康快速发展。

Please take over our great field and improve it! Write papers that develop new, more powerful methods! Criticise the work of the older generation and do better! Find new topics to research that we have overlooked! In this way the field can move forward and provide ever increasing value to science.

Thelwall, Michael (University of Sheffield, UK)

2023.6.11

Since the 1930s scientists, beginning in Poland (Ossowska and Ossowski, 1935), are studying science itself. But even these scholars had predecessors such as de Candolle (Switzerland), Galton (UK), Lotka (USA), and Gross & Gross (USA). Moreover, techniques used in fields such as economics (Pareto), linguistics (Zipf) and geography (Auerbach) were later used in scientometrics and bibliometrics. Unfortunately, over the years scientometrics and bibliometrics became more and more focused on evaluation, not only on a large scale (countries, universities) but even on individuals. Not surprisingly, the use of quantitative indicators was abused by some (playing the numbers game), leading to calls to abandon bibliometrics (by those who did not understand the purpose of the field as a whole). It is my sincere hope that young students when reading this book, will understand the richness of our field, whatever its name (science of science, scientometrics, bibliometrics, informetrics).

Ronald Rousseau (KU Leuven & University of Antwerp, Belgium)

2023.6.12

It is important to take a course on mathematics (at least bachelor degree) before starting informetric research. This is the only way to upgrade the field of informetrics to a real science instead of merely a field of data gathering and making superficial conclusions based on it. It is also important to have knowledge of neighboring fields (such as econometrics, biometrics, ...) so that one can avoid drawing conclusions that have been made before in these other fields.

Leo Egghe(Hasselt University, Belgium)

2023.6.13

In the half century since we wrote *Evaluative Bibliometrics* (Narin 1976) the data available for Scientometrics has expanded exponentially, the methodologies have expanded hundred folds, but the challenge of policy relevance remains. Our continued access to public funding requires that we demonstrate relevance to public policy. We must strive for indicators that capture the essence of important research advances, the tops of the distributions, the science that is really important, rather than try to learn more and more about less and less. We should aim for indicators that are understandable to users, both academic and policy, and outside as well as inside of our community. There is still much of importance that we can do to foster scientific advance: to do so we must make our findings clear and our indicators relevant. I am reminded of the statement by the Nobel laureate Peter Medawar in his book 'Advice to a young scientist': "any scientist of any age who wants to make important discoveries must study important problems" (Medawar 1979: 13).

Francis Narin (Retired President, CHI Research, USA)

2023.6.13

Welcome to the new generation of bibliometricians/scientometricians. My best advice, to young and old, is to value serendipity when it offers you an opportunity, a chance for collaboration, a new or previously unrecognized data source and the like. Think laterally – if you encounter something interesting, could it be applied to your research? Could a technique from one discipline be brought into yours, to add to your tool kit and bring new insights? What is going on in a subject field that would be interesting to explore using the quantitative tools we have? And don't forget about the scholars who are producing the literature and other data sources we study. Small scale studies looking at interesting phenomena in a field where you can chat with the participants can be as valuable as another rummage through that mega-data set.

Katherine W. McCain (Drexel University, USA)

2023.6.13

The advice I would give young scientometricians and those new to the field is to try to think of some way to expand the boundaries of the field. Scientometrics has many different subareas from studies of individual papers or scientists to studies of research areas or disciplines to analyses of institutions, countries, and science policy. Whatever your focus, study the existing literature and try to come up with some new point of departure. Perhaps it is a new mathematical tool or uses a method imported from some other field. Or it might be a new kind of data or a combination of existing data sources.

Ask yourself what you are interested in finding out. For example, I have been interested in the history and philosophy of science, and what makes scientific knowledge different from other forms of knowledge, what leads scientists to reach a consensus, how does scientific knowledge change, and how are scientific findings confirmed? Of course, these are very old problems and much has been written about them. The challenge is to find some new point of departure that no one else has attempted. If you were trained in science, you can start by picking an area that is familiar to you and where you have insight or expertise. Or start from another field such as economics or psychology and think how it impacts science. Another approach is to critique some previous school of thought such as Mertonian norms, social construction of knowledge, the use of citation counts for evaluation, or the interpretation of maps of science. Don't be afraid to offend other researchers but always have good reasons for your criticisms.

Scientometrics has traditionally dealt with databases of scientific papers. But your approach may take you beyond counts of papers or citations to the detailed consideration of scientific ideas or institutions. Other sources of data might include interviews with scientists, social media, full text analyses, including citation contexts, or even new large language models and software. AI offers many new methods including classification and summarization. Many researchers are now interested in social issues such as gender studies or minority representation in science. I would avoid trendy topics unless you have new ideas or novel data that can be brought to bear. These are the kinds of expansions of boundaries that I believe Scientometrics needs and will foster the growth and increase the vitality of the field. Good luck.

Henry Small (SciTech Strategies Inc,USA)

2023.6.14

The research system plays a crucial role in satisfying human curiosity, promoting technological progress, and addressing global societal challenges. Given the huge scale of the scientific enterprise and the large amounts of resources invested, proper management of the system is absolutely critical. By providing quantitative data-driven insights into the current state of the research system and its ongoing development, scientometrics (or quantitative science studies) offers essential information to manage the system and to steer it in new directions. I consider it a big privilege to be in the position to contribute to this. Let's all work together to keep improving the data sources and the methods that we use in our scientometric work, and let's make sure we serve the research system, and society at large, in the best possible way!

Ludo Waltman (CWTS, Leiden University)

2023.6.17

There are many crucial steps in bibliometric analysis where mistakes are often made. Here we mention three. First, the problem you are trying to solve should be both important and well posed. Second, the data you use must be the right data for the problem rather than just the data that are available. Third, analysis and observations can rarely be extrapolated with any robustness. These three principles lead to some do's and don'ts in bibliometric analysis.

Regarding problems, DO work on problems that matter, where the results can lead to action that creates positive change in the world. DO think deeply about your research problems and anticipate ways to increase robustness and trust in your results. DON'T work on problems just because you have a particular dataset.

Regarding data, DO identify what data is needed for analysis. DON'T settle for using the data you can get easily - it may not be sufficient. DO the hard work to understand what your data can and can't do. DO learn about how your data sources were created. DO get your hands dirty - work manually with the data and develop a gut-level understanding of its strengths and limitations. DON'T trust data you get from others until you have examined it closely.

Regarding analysis, DO try to disprove your results. DON'T believe them at first. If your analysis is field-specific, DO restrict your observations and conclusions to that field. DON'T extrapolate without justification. DO look for the reasons underlying the phenomena you see - this greatly increases the robustness of the analysis. DON'T just report numbers without looking for the underlying stories.

We wish you success in your future endeavors.

Kevin Boyack and Dick Klavans(SciTech Strategies Inc,USA)

2023.6.18

All statistical analysis, in general, and scientometric analysis, in particular, can be compared to the preparation of a meal. The main elements are the raw materials, the preparation methods (cooking, baking), and the serving. In scientometrics, the raw materials are the bibliographic data sources and the raw data sets that can be extracted from them. Data preparation is as important as properly marinating meat or baking pasta; cooking is the use of “recipes” or algorithms to determine indicators. Finally, serving is the presentation of the final results.

The choice of which dish to prepare from a cookbook may depend on the raw materials available, of course, but the choice of raw materials and recipes depends above all on the purpose of cooking: a quick and nutritious meal for oneself, a spectacular meal for one's guests, or a special dietary meal for a convalescent. Nathan Myhrvold, the "pope of modernist cooking," warns: Good food can only come from good ingredients. There was a time when this basic truth was appreciated only by the finest chefs. Today, it seems that the entire food world is placing more and more emphasis on the quality of ingredients.

A truth worth considering. Even the most sophisticated algorithms cannot compensate for the shortcomings of the original data. Analyses using data from free databases can, at best, provide approximate results.

But it is also worth remembering the admonition of the statistician John W. Tukey: It is much better to have an approximate answer to a vaguely formulated but correct question than an exact answer to a precisely formulated but incorrect question.

András Schubert (Hungarian Academy of Sciences, Budapest, Hungary)

2023.6.19

"Bibliometrics" is an attempt to capture science networks that are generated by research activity and to then help to understand the dynamics of knowledge in its political and socio-economic environment, which is the object of scientometrics. Evaluation comes as an application among others of this multi-network of actors and related aspects: affiliation, collaboration, citation, linguistic/semantic contents, etc. The magic of numbers can hide data and methods biases - handling of very skew distributions with strong influence of micro events on macro states (e.g. pioneers' oeuvre) with also visibility biases, a dark side of the Matthew effect, mostly observed in other social networks. Many obstacles can hinder the international knowledge system, such as external constraints on circulation of information, citations, etc. Scientometrics can shed light on that treasure of universal communication, including on the "strength of weak ties", which is so vital for interdisciplinarity and breakthroughs. Another upcoming issue is that of monitoring the potential of artificial intelligence in the shaping of knowledge, with the open question: will AI enhance creativity or favour conformism? There is no doubt that AI is a challenge for scientometrics, too.

Michel Zitt (Lereco lab, Nantes, France)

2023.6.19

Scientometrics offers a powerful set of tools for understanding how the world of science (or research more widely) operates. But never forget that bibliometric data are merely imperfect or partial indicators of a complex reality, and considerable work is needed to clarify exactly what concepts they relate to and how and to what extent. They should be used carefully and, wherever possible, in combination with other approaches, in particular interviews, before attempting to arrive at conclusions as to what is happening in science.

Ben Martin(University of Sussex Business School, UK)

2023.6.20

Scientometrics is not limited to the natural sciences nor to the mathematics of bibliographic core-and-scatter distributions. The literatures of all fields generate such distributions, and they consist not only of numeric data but of verbal data as well. That is, they consist of bibliographic sources ranked high-to-low by counts of the items they produce in response to a seed term, and those sources have names. Names have meanings, and the names brought together by the rankings can often be interpreted jointly. For that reason, I have referred to core-and-scatter distributions as “bibliograms”—as messages that can be read for their human interest. For instance, in the English-speaking West there is a literary field called redology, which is the academic study of Cao Zuequin’s *Dream of the Red Chamber* (in Chinese and in English or other translations). If the name of that novel is entered as a subject-heading into one version of WorldCat (OCLC’s international union catalog), it retrieves the books with that heading ranked by how many OCLC member libraries hold each book. That result shows which editions of the novel and which critical and historical monographs on it are most widely held—the library “best sellers” of redology, so to speak. There’s a study in that! I mention all this simply to convey my own take on scientometrics, which you may not have considered—its potential relevance to non-quantitative people in the social sciences and even the humanities.

Howard D. White (Drexel University, USA)

2023.6.21

From bibliometrics toward scientometrics

The future of societies depends primarily on the social and economic development that is strongly influenced by science and technology. The advance of science can be followed by scientometric methods quantitatively. Accordingly, scientometrics is a science on science for science.

From practical aspects one of the most important fields of scientometrics is the evaluation of scientific performance of individuals, teams, countries, fields, etc. This means primarily the assessment of quantity and impact of scientific publications.

The essence of scientometrics (primarily: that of evaluative scientometrics) is the indicator. The mission of scientometricians is to offer relevant data, methods and indicators for scientists, science politicians and managers for making appropriate decisions when initiating new research directions, selecting relevant topics, nominating research heads or distributing grants, etc. A country or a university should grant promising research fields and talented scientists because „giants on the shoulder of giants could see further” (Newton) than dwarfs on dwarfs.

It is often neglected that any evaluation requires: setting goals, selecting appropriate data and elaborating relevant indicators. One has to keep in mind that numbers are not data and data are not indicators. The bibliometric conditions of the evaluated items may be rather different, consequently, relative indices and appropriate reference standards are needed.

The basic assumptions in evaluative scientometrics – information unit of sciences is the scientific paper and unit of impact is the citation - are crude approximations, but they work in most science fields in practice.

Each scientometric system (i.e. publications, citations, etc. of an individual, team, institute, country, topic, field, etc.) is unique. Therefore the general rules should be adopted to the special systems to be assessed.

I am convinced, responsibility of scientometricians for the correctness of their results is high as they may strongly influence the future of science.

Péter Vinkler (Research Centre for Natural Sciences, Hungary)

2023.6.27

The quantitative study of science is mostly referred to as scientometrics. Within scientometrics, the research on scientific communication, particularly with data from publications, patents, citations, and journals is called bibliometrics. The development of a relatively new field such as scientometrics as an ‘accepted’ field within the academic community goes hand in hand with the rise and flourishing of institutes and research groups that shape the field. Without such an institutionalization, a field will disappear from the academic scene or swallowed up by other fields. Scientometric research was tremendously stimulated by the most crucial breakthrough in the history of the quantitative studies of science, the creation of the Science Citation Index (SCI). This unprecedented availability of data stimulated the development of scientometric analytical methods, particularly advanced bibliometric research performance indicators and science maps. This development had and still has the clear goal to identify, within the enormous amount of current research work all over the world, those researchers and their scientific activities that really matter in advancing our knowledge, not seldom pioneering work hidden in the mass.

It is interesting to find out to what extent all the new databases that have been developed since the SCI are providing us really new data with substantial added values for the above formulated goal. At the same time the indicators and maps originally developed for application offer us a set of effective instruments for basic research on the development of the science system. Provided of course that we (we = all scientometrics researchers, including the newcomers...) are well educated and experienced in mathematical methods and, particularly, in statistics. And given that scientometrics is a data-intensive field, that we are supported by computer science experts and relevant facilities. And also, crucially important, that we have the ability to connect scientometrics successfully with fields such as economics, psychology, physics, urban studies, and other fields of science that may inspire to new approaches, new methods, new kind of data. But also, earlier literature is still a gold mine of fascinating topics that have never been followed up on, problems that have gone unaddressed.

We have to guard against tendencies to use scientometric methods primarily for ‘steering’ science in directions that are prescribed by current, often political correctness-driven goals. Certainly, most of these goals are socially legitimate but such a use of scientometrics must not work to the detriment of fundamental research. Besides all the discussions about relevance to our society, it is interesting to take a look at the scientific knowledge that is rejected or ignored by the same society. In other words, the gap between what we know and what we do. For all fields of science, and also for scientometrics, the most important ability is to find and to work on the crucial problems. An example are science maps: what do they really represent, why are they ‘flat’, how to construct continuous time-series of maps. And in the interface between science and technology, particularly the role of instrumentation in the advancement of science. Enough unknown territory is waiting to be explored...

Anthony van Raan (CWTS, Leiden University, the Netherlands)

2023.6.28

Some young scientists may have the great luck and honour to meet or even collaborate with pioneers in the field of their activity. As a young scientist, I was one of these privileged persons and learning from the first generation of scientometricians have had a decisive influence on my professional career. This first generation, renowned scientists with professional backgrounds from various fields, in which they were still working but, at the same time, conducting professional scientometric research, have come up with visions and ideas for quantifying and measuring various aspects of scientific research and scholarly communication. They often used models, methods and ways of thinking brought in from their own fields and incorporated those into the new contexts of interdisciplinary research in information science. And they often collected and prepared the necessary data themselves, sometimes even manually. What I learned from the first generation is mainly two-fold. The first issue is, that retrieving, cleaning and processing appropriate data for the use in quantitative science studies is a long and stony road that demands modesty and patience. The second one is more complex as this regards interdisciplinarity in more general terms. Becoming a researcher is not only the result of purposefully studying but is also shaped by specific socialisation processes that may differ from field to field. Collaborating with scientists from other fields does therefore not only broaden the own professional horizon but also helps better understand the subjects to which scientometrics is applied and that models and techniques may not simply be migrated and applied to other contexts without the necessary adjustments.

I consider myself part of the “second” generation of scientometricians, who gradually moved from the own field to scientometrics. I still learned collecting and correcting data manually, timidly and reverently watching hesitantly turning magnetic tapes, working at the mainframe computer at nights (because of cheaper CPU time), experienced some years later that the content of forty magnetic tapes can fit on one CD-ROM, and authors may have names even longer than eleven characters. Finally, the time arrived when source data became part of a huge global data network with nearly unlimited storage place. This spectacular evolution went hand in hand with the development of scientometric tools and the associated software. Finally, this second generation also largely contributed to the institutionalisation of the field so that apart from the institutionalised scholarly communication (with journals, books, workshops, conferences), the field has become part of higher education as well. The members of the “third” generation have increasingly become scientists skilled in scientometrics, informetrics or closely related fields.

My advice to young researchers in our field is based on my own experience, namely, to consider these achievements a gift, an offer but also a challenge that deserves the necessary respect. The retrieval, preparation of clean and proper data, the choice of appropriate models, the development and application of sound methodology and contributing with meaningful and valid outcomes is a hard job but is still imperative in doing research in scientometrics. Despite the breath-taking development we have witnessed during the last decades, the experiences and insights of the previous generations in this respect still hold for present-day research too.

Wolfgang Glänzel (KU Leuven, Belgium) 2023.7.11

Scientometrics in relation to Information Retrieval

When carrying out scientometric (including webometric and altmetric) analyses the gathering of data is crucial to the analytic outcome. From the 60es manual as well as (semi)automatic information retrieval (IR) is hence applied to online databases of various kinds and, in recent decades, also to the WWW. Aside from citation databases like Scopus and Web of Science, field-dependent and institutional repositories as well as Web crawlers are used to gather data – depending on the purpose of the scientometric analysis. In such cases IR involves a high degree of knowledge of field structures and retrieval possibilities in the databases used. However, often the IR options are made very limited due to commercial secrets, e.g., in search engines like Google and Bing; one hardly knows why the retrieval outcome looks the way it does. One should remember that Google originally (and falsely) in 1998 assumed web inlinks to be like citations, that is, the more inlinks to an object, the more recognized it is, and thus assumed (again falsely) more relevant. But it worked. Later on Google began to mix many other parameters to produce its ranked lists of objects. Bing's retrieval algorithms was originally based on text-based IR research and relevance as understood in IR; other parameters are supposedly also included. In addition, the two search engines' crawlers are retrieving different data when crawling the Web. Hence, it is always a good idea to search both engines for the same query, download the data and find the overlap as well as separate information. Another important limitation is the question of coverage of the data source used. In the cases of the large and recognized field-dependent and citation databases one may argue that the latter cover almost all the central journals in the academic landscape, although there are smaller differences detected in some academic fields between Scopus and Web of Science. Hence, one can argue that the extraction from those sources does not constitute a sample but is the actual population. This can be seen in contrast to most webometric and altmetric measures for which analyses commonly operate with samples of unknown populations. Thus, coverage, sampling and the way data is combined in the scientometric analysis influence the way statistics should be carried out.

Finally, one should not overlook the possibilities lying in the application of citations to IR, mainly investigated in recent years (Belter, 2017). In contrast to web links real academic citations have a purpose following a social scientific code, for the most part of neutral or positive nature and generated by humans. One may see a citation as a representation of an interpretation (anchor text, Garfield, 1979) by the citer on the cited work, additional to other kinds of representation and other interpretations, e.g. by other citers, human or artificial indexers, abstract generators, etc. (poly representation, Ingwersen & Jarvelin, 2005; Ingwersen, 2012). The assumption is that citations (and in particular the immediate citing context surrounding the reference placed in the citing text) may have 'something' to do with relevance of (parts of) the cited document and hence be applied as a tool for (re)ranking of documents (Larsen, 2002). There are important issues and limitations to be tested in this approach to IR: The time issue: how far back do we have to go? – perhaps using citing/cited half-life? Using cited journal and/or citing journal impact factor for re-ranking of retrieval results? Using total

citations to cited items as well as author and/or citing author impact (h-index) in addition – or should citation scores be limited to recommendation of documents? Can co-citation be usefully applied, e.g. in pseudo relevance feedback? How does uncitedness (up to 70 % in a field) and multi-disciplinarity influence the retrieval outcome when applying citations? There are many questions to be tested in the future.

Peter Ingwersen (University of Copenhagen, Denmark)

2023. 9.16

12. 扩展资料

[点击标题直接进入全文](#)

CiteSpace 学习集合

1. CiteSpace 基础

[CiteSpace 基础 001: 下载及安装](#)
[CiteSpace 基础 002: 软件原理](#)
[CiteSpace 基础 003: 最新安装视频](#)
[CiteSpace 基础 004: 不同版本使用说明](#)
[CiteSpace 基础 005: 知识图谱理论与实践](#)
[CiteSpace 理论基础与技术](#)
[CiteSpace 软件界面与功能](#)
[CiteSpace 对 CNKI 数据的分析](#)
[CiteSpace 对 CSSCI 数据的分析](#)
[CiteSpace 对 Web of Science 数据的分析](#)
[CiteSpace 对 RSCI 俄罗斯科学索引数据分析](#)
[CiteSpace 引文网络主路径分析](#)
[CiteSpace 对结构变异的分析](#)
[CiteSpace 的设计和分析原理](#)
[CiteSpace 的分析流程](#)

2. CiteSpace 可视化设计

[CiteSpace 视图 001: 时区视图](#)
[CiteSpace 视图 002: 网络视图](#)
[CiteSpace 视图 003: 网络叠加图](#)
[CiteSpace 视图 004: 期刊叠加视图](#)
[CiteSpace 视图 005: 时间线视图](#)
[CiteSpace 视图 006: 主题配色](#)

3. CiteSpace 案例图

[案例 001: CiteSpace 最新案例图](#)
[案例 002: CiteSpace 最新案例图](#)
[案例 003: CiteSpace 最新案例图](#)
[案例 004: CiteSpace 最新案例图](#)
[案例 005: CiteSpace 最新案例图](#)
[案例 006: CiteSpace 最新案例图](#)

案例 007: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 008: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 009: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 010: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 011: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 012: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 013: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 014: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 015: CiteSpace 最新案例图
案例 016: CiteSpace 最新案例图 (主题图)

4. CiteSpace 案例论文目录

CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2021(1), 1-100
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2021(2), 101-200
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2021(3), 201-300
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2021(4), 301-400
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2021(5), 401-500
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2021(6), 501-545
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2020 学位论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 2014-2019 学位论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 10 篇 CiteSpace 知识图谱博士论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 10 篇情报科学知识图谱学位论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 14 篇医学科学知识图谱博士论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 10 篇教育科学知识图谱学位论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 10 篇体育科学知识图谱学位论文
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 图谱案例著作
CiteSpace 实践与应用: 图谱案例论文

5. CiteSpace 问题

问题 001: CiteSpace 论文问题
问题 002: CiteSpace 论文问题
问题 003: CiteSpace 论文问题
CiteSpace 问答 001: 常见问题
CiteSpace 问答 002: 分析中的异常要自己检查和完善
CiteSpace 问答 003: 关于国家或地区合作和关键词分析

6. 科学知识图谱基础

基础知识 001: 文献共被引分析

基础知识 002: 科研合作网络分析
基础知识 003: 研究主题分析
基础知识 004: 地理可视化
基础知识 005: 科学计量与知识图谱免费指南
基础知识 006: 科学知识图谱典型案例视频
基础知识 007: 认识三计学
基础知识 008: 数据库与数据采集
基础知识 009: 科学知识图谱理论、方法与实践

7. 科学知识图谱基础视频

视频 001: CiteSpace 视频
视频 002: BibExcel 视频
视频 003: VOSviewer 视频
视频 004: SCI2 视频
视频 005: R-Bibliometrix 视频
视频 006: SCIMAT 视频
视频 007: 文献计量中的基础概念
视频 008: 不同领域的 Bibliometrics

VOSViewer 学习集合

1. VOSviewer 基础

VOSviewer 基础 001: 入门视频 (英文)
VOSviewer 基础 002: 中文指南 (正式出版)
VOSviewer 基础 003: 中文指南 (免费版)
VOSviewer 基础 004: 知网数据分析
VOSviewer 基础 005: 在线版发布
VOSviewer 对文献耦合的分析
VOSviewer 对作者合作的分析
VOSviewer 结合 POP 对文本主题的挖掘
VOSviewer 下载和安装
VOSviewer 对网络文件的可视化
VOSviewer 对文本主题的挖掘
VOSviewer 对文本主题的挖掘 (2)
VOSviewer 文献共被引的分析
VOSviewer 科学领域的叠加分析
VOSviewer 科学期刊的叠加分析

VOSviewer 分析 PubMed 数据
VOSviewer 分析 Scopus 数据
CitNetExplorer 软件下载与安装
CitNetExplorer 分析和可视化文献引证网络
KML 文件的地理可视化

2. VOSviewer 可视化设计

VOSviewer 视图 001: 网络图
VOSviewer 视图 002: 叠加图
VOSviewer 视图 003: 密度图

3. VOSviewer 案例图

案例 001: VOSviewer 最新案例图
案例 002: VOSviewer 最新案例图
案例 003: VOSviewer 最新案例图
案例 004: VOSviewer 最新案例图
案例 005: VOSviewer 最新案例图
案例 006: VOSviewer 最新案例图
在线浏览 Engineering 期刊主题分布图
在线浏览全球 1500 余名火灾学者的合作网络
在线浏览 Fire Safety Journal 主题分布图
在线浏览 Ludo 的合作网络
在线浏览《安全与环境学报》主题分布
在线浏览中科大火灾实验室师生网络图

4. VOSviewer 实践

VOSviewer 实践与应用: 2011-2020
VOSviewer 实践与应用: 论文产出趋势

5. 科学知识图谱基础

基础知识 001: 文献共被引分析
基础知识 002: 科研合作网络分析
基础知识 003: 研究主题分析
基础知识 004: 地理可视化
基础知识 005: 科学计量与知识图谱免费指南
基础知识 006: 科学知识图谱典型案例视频
基础知识 007: 认识三计学
基础知识 008: 数据库与数据采集
基础知识 009: 科学知识图谱理论、方法与实践

6. 科学知识图谱基础视频

- 视频 001: CiteSpace 视频
- 视频 002: BibExcel 视频
- 视频 003: VOSviewer 视频
- 视频 004: SCI2 视频
- 视频 005: R-Bibliometrix 视频
- 视频 006: SCIMAT 视频
- 视频 007: 文献计量中的基础概念
- 视频 008: 不同领域的 Bibliometrics

扩展阅读

- 科学计量与知识图谱系列图书
- 科学知识前沿图谱绘制工具总结
- 科学知识前沿图谱资料合集
- 普赖斯奖人物: 加菲尔德先生
- 普赖斯奖人物: 鲁特·雷切斯多夫
- 普赖斯奖人物: 卢多·瓦特曼
- 科学知识图谱可视化设计 001: 叠加图
- 科学知识图谱可视化设计 002: 时间线
- 科学知识图谱论文很好发表吗?
- ISSI 2021 论文集下载

BibExcel 学习集合

BibExcel 基础

1. BIBEXCEL 软件下载
2. BIBEXCEL 界面概览及常见文件
3. BIBEXCEL 对 CNKI 的转换和分析
4. BIBEXCEL 对 CSCD 的转换和分析
5. BIBEXCEL 对 CSSCI 的转换与分析
6. BIBEXCEL 对 KCI 的转换和分析
7. BIBEXCEL 对 RCI 的转换和分析
8. SCOPUS+BibExcel 数据的检索及转换
9. WEB OF SCIENCE+BibExcel 数据的检索与转换
10. BibExcel 分析德温特专利数据

11. BIBEXCEL 从标题中提取主题进行共词分析
11. BIBEXCEL 从标题中提取主题进行共词分析
13. BIBEXCEL 分析 wos 地址信息
14. BIBEXCEL 分析作者的合作网络
15. BIBEXCEL 计算 H 指数
16. BIBEXCEL 计算出现矩阵和共现强度
17. BIBEXCEL 进行文献共被引分析
18. BIBEXCEL 进行知识单元频次统计
19. BIBEXCEL 利用 THE LIST 过滤词
20. BIBEXCEL 领域期刊编委的共现网络
21. SCOPUS 数据转换为 wos 格式
22. LOET 工具提取 WOS 知识单元
23. PAJEK 对网络聚类及节点的计算
24. BIBEXCEL 文件导入 VOSVIEWER 进行可视化

科学知识图谱基础

- 基础知识 001：文献共被引分析
- 基础知识 002：科研合作网络分析
- 基础知识 003：研究主题分析
- 基础知识 004：地理可视化
- 基础知识 005：科学计量与知识图谱免费指南
- 基础知识 006：科学知识图谱典型案例视频
- 基础知识 007：认识三计学
- 基础知识 008：数据库与数据采集
- 基础知识 009：科学知识图谱理论、方法与实践
- 谁最早提出“文献计量学”这个词？
- 文献计量学指标应用的四个群体

13. 元科学专业委员会

2023年3月30日，北京科学技术情报学会（Beijing Science & Technology Information Society）第十届理事会听取了李杰关于“元科学专业委员会”筹建的报告，审议通过了成立北京科学技术情报学会元科学专业委员会（Metasciences Committee）的决议，以促进从元科学视角认识科学发展的规律和特征，更好地服务于新时期科技情报与科技政策等工作。

元科学专业委员会的主题架构见图4，主要分为三个方面：1）量化科学元勘研究（quantitative science studies），包含科学计量学、文献计量学、信息计量学以及替代计量学等主题。该主题群主要由数据科学家和科技情报专家组成，以科技数据驱动科学认知和情报发现；2）科学学与科学哲学（science of science, philosophy of science），由涉及科技史、科技哲学以及科学学研究的专家学者组成。3）科学、技术与创新政策研究（science, technology, innovation & policy），该方面主要由从事科技政策、智库科学与工程、区域与国别科技态势、创新原理等方面的专家组成。元科学专业委员会以综合集成科学（integrated science）方法论为指导思想，以形成多维度多视角的科学发展认知模式。专业委员会倡导在诚信、负责任的基础上开展创新活动，以开放、包容、透明和共享为基本理念开展学术研究和交流工作。

图6 元科学专业委员会主题架构图
(元科学学术年会主题)

第一届元科学专业委员会由来自全国各地高校、研究所、企业等组织或单位的60位专家学者组成。其中，顾问1人，主任1人，副主任4人，秘书长1人。专委会邀请樊春良研究员（中国科学院科技战略咨询研究院）担任顾问；主任委员由委员会的发起和组织者李杰副研究员（中国科学院文献情报中心）

担任；副主任委员分别为赵勇研究馆员（中国农业大学）、吴登生研究员（中国科学院科技战略咨询研究院）、杜建助理教授（北京大学健康医疗大数据国家研究院）以及欧阳昭连研究员（中国医学科学院医学信息研究所）；专委会秘书长由付宏（北京市科学技术研究院科技智库中心）担任。总体上，元科学专业委员会委员组成了以“量化科学研究”方向的学者为主，联合科学学、科技哲学、科学史学等领域学者的学术共同体。专委会倡导“以定性定量相结合的综合集成方法论来认识科学，并力求为复杂信息环境下的科技决策提供方案”。

元科学专业委员会成立以来，开通了微信公众号“开放科学计量学实验室（Open Scientometrics Lab）”，并积极围绕“元科学专业委员会主题架构图”策划学术或科普活动。目前，专委会主要的学术活动有“元科学学术年会（Metasciences Conference）”和“数智时代的科技情报实践工作坊（图 5）”等。

图 7 数智时代的科技情报实践工作坊架构